

Analysis of Impulsive Buying Behavior in Fashion Industry

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ABSTRACT

In this era of rising customer expectations and intense competitions, marketers and retailers constantly look towards means to maximize their customers' share of wallet, in terms of additional sales. Marketers, today, thus focus on the customers' preferences, their needs and wishes with an aim to maximize it. Impulse shopping can be termed as a spontaneous, immediate purchase without pre-shopping intentions either to buy a specific product category or to fulfil a specific buying task. Impulse buying is a major research concern among marketers due to its pervasive aspects of consumer behavior as well as its potential in the marketing world. Based on the literature review, and after considering the questions we want to answer, the research problem of the research paper is "Analysis of Impulse Buying Behavior in the Fashion Industry". This problem would specifically be emphasizing on the factors which affect such behavior, post purchase feelings and behavior and how online shopping has increased the propensity of such behavior. Based on the research problem of our paper, given below are the 4 major objectives which the paper will studying and analysing:

1. Determining and comparing the various internal and external factors which affect Impulse Buying Behavior in the Fashion Industry.
2. Analysing The Impulse Buying Behavior Towards Different Fashion Product Categories
3. Analysing The Post Purchase Feeling and Behavior as A Result of Impulse Buying Behavior
4. Determining the impact of growing E-commerce industry on impulse shopping behavior in the fashion industry, and the factors leading to it.

Methodology used in research paper is SINGLE CROSS SECTIONAL DESCRIPTIVE DESIGN. Given the objective and design of our research, we will be using basic descriptive statistics i.e. Mean, Median and Mode to compare and analyse our data and conclude our findings.

Finally, the findings for the research essentially indicated that amongst the external factors, Overall store environment and lower prices played a pivotal role. Moreover, males tend to shop more impulsively as compared to females. Customers tend to show a positive impulse behavior towards Footwear and Clothing items. Happiness is seen to be the most common post purchase behavior. Lastly, the research also presented an evidence showing that the emergence of e-commerce positively impacted impulse buying behavior, with Heavy Discounting being its most prominent driver.

Keywords-- Impulse Buying Behavior, Fashion Industry, Apparel Impulse Shopping, Factor Affect Impulse Shopping, Post Purchase Behavior, Online Impulse Shopping

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Meaning

In this era of rising customer expectations and intense competitions, marketers and retailers constantly look towards means to maximize their customers' share of wallet, in terms of additional sales. Marketers, today, thus focus on the customers' preferences, their needs and wishes with an aim to maximize it.

Customer behaviour is the most complex issue of marketing, due to its heterogenic and multi-layered nature. One such specific customer behaviour on the market is impulse buying behaviour. Consumers engage in impulse buying when they experience a sudden but powerful persistent urge to buy product offers immediately without due regard to the consequences of buying the offering.

In simple words, impulse shopping can be termed as a spontaneous, immediate purchase without pre-shopping intentions either to buy a specific product category or to fulfil a specific buying task. Impulse buying is a major research concern among marketers due to its pervasive aspects of consumer behavior as well as its potential in the marketing world.

1.2 Factors

Marketers and retailers today tend to exploit such impulse buying behaviour, based on certain specific factors and drives. For example, a person shopping in a retail store might not want to buy a chocolate bar, however looking at it being displayed at the checkout aisle, he might be induced to buy one. Alternately, a person shopping in a happy or a joyous mood, might not have planned to buy a pastry, while shopping for bread at a bakery, does buy one solely because of his good mood. Thus, impulse shopping in general is broadly affected by two factors i.e. Internal and External.

Internal Factors include changing moods, income, gender and general demographics of the customer.

External factors, although are usual specific to the product category in question, but can be generalised into price, store environment, promotional schemes, visual display, etc.

1.3 Fashion Industry

The Indian retail market is expected to demonstrate a promising year-on-year growth of 6 percent to reach US \$865 billion, by 2023, from the current US \$490 billion. The share of apparel in India's retail market is 8 percent, corresponding to a value of US \$40 billion. In addition to fashion apparel, the growing

demand for fashion accessories makes the Indian fashion market both interesting and lucrative.

The fashion and apparel industry in India has emerged as one of the most dynamic and rapidly growing industries with several domestic and foreign players entering into the market. Researchers have also found that Indian consumers have diametrically changed in terms of their shopping behaviour and impulse buying is emerging as a highly noticeable behaviour due to entry of foreign products in Indian market, growth in organized retail industry, increasing disposable income, favourable demographic segmentation and changing culture & lifestyle.

Thus marketers can take advantage of this situation by studying the various factors which could possibly affect such impulse behavior, while considering the specific types of fashion products which are most likely to be purchased on an impulse.

1.4 Emergence of Online Shopping

Out of \$7 billion India's e-tailing market, online fashion retail stands with \$2.4 billion contributions to it. While this estimation for Indian e-tailing market is expected to touch \$60 Billion by 2020 and online Fashion Retail Market is expected to reach \$20 Billion by 2020. Given the expansion of online apparel shopping (complimented by heavy advertising and better discounts), one can expect such an increase to positively contribute towards impulse buying behavior, specifically in the fashion industry.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This topic is about factors affecting Impulse buying behaviours in people of all age groups and the post purchase feelings associated with it. The topic also differentiates between the different kinds of products and their likeliness to be bought on an impulse. This paper focuses specifically on the fashion industry. Namely Clothing, Footwear, Accessories and cosmetics.

Online Impulse Buying

Under normal circumstances an individual usually rationally compares his alternatives and then chooses the most viable option while making a purchase. Impulse buying however, is a situation that emerges from spontaneity. A consumer does not necessarily think through his buying decision. E - Commerce through smart algorithms plague social media with their flashy targeted advertisements and make seem to make it easier for an individual to fall prey to shopping impulsively.

In Javeria Zulfiqar, Gulfam Ambreen and Mazia Fateen Bushra's paper for online purchases ease of using websites, website quality, information available on websites, reliability/ honouring commitments and security and privacy of the information pertaining to the customers are all important factors. (Akyuz, 2018)

Gender Differences

Typically, the male gender seems to be more inclined to buying impulsively than their female

counterparts. These findings are backed by Parmar Vishnu and Ahmed Rizwan Raheem in their paper that states that the male to female ratio in impulse buying is nearly 3:1 respectively. Another paper by Anmol Rasheed Et Al has found that 61% of buyers are male and 39% are female. (Atilla, 2013)

Other Factors

When it comes to factors other than the gender of said buyer - schemes, discounts and lower prices are more attractive than the overall shopping environment and aesthetic appeal of the store according to Anmol Rasheed Et Al. In a paper by Umair Akram, Peng Hui, Muhammad Kaleem Khan, Chen Yan and Zubair Akram they found that likeness to online impulse shop edged out all other kinds of shopping avenues studied. (Factors Affecting)

Visual merchandising and packaging play a role in attracting customers especially when it comes to FMCG products as deduced by Parmar Vishnu and Ahmed Rizwan Raheem in their paper. (Rasheed, 2017) (RAHEEM2, 2013)

Post Purchase Mood

While discussing the psychology of an impulse purchase an individual's pre purchase and post purchase mood come into question. According to a blog by Madeline Ford psychologists agree that people with a propensity to shop impulsively have a general trait of impulsivity in their everyday life as well.

Personal factors pre and post purchase seem to affect this buying behaviour as well. The time an individual spends in a store the more likely they are to purchase an item as stated by Muruganthanam and bhakat in their study.

According to a paper published by Leyla Ozer and Beyza Gultekin the post purchase mood after impulse buying is highly undeterred. Around 81% of the consumers seem to be satisfied and happy with their buy post purchase. (Bhakat, 2013) (Ford, 2013)

III. RESEARCH PROBLEM

Based on the literature review, and after considering the questions that need to be answered, the research problem of the research paper is "Analysis of Impulse Buying Behavior in the Fashion Industry". This problem would specifically be emphasizing on the factors which affect such behavior, post purchase feelings and behavior and how online shopping has increased the propensity of such behavior.

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Based on the research problem of our paper, given below are the 4 major objectives which the paper will studying and analysing:

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V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research Design

A research design is a basic plan that guides the data collection and analysis phases of the research project. It provides the framework that specifies the type of information to be collected, its sources and collection procedure.

A research design can be divided into 3 broad types, based on the type of research that is to be conducted. The 3 types are Descriptive, Exploratory and Causal.

Descriptive design, as the name suggests describes and studies the characteristics and facts related to a specific problem or phenomenon, within a given population. Given that our research essentially revolves around studying the phenomenon of impulse buying behavior, we have used a descriptive design for our research.

Moreover, descriptive design can be further divided into 2 types, longitudinal and cross-sectional. Longitudinal studies are the ones which are done with the help of a panel. Data is collected from this group multiple number of times and different time periods on the same variable. On the other and, cross sectional study is the one where data is collected from the population only once during a particular period of time.

Since our research is conducted at a specific point of time, from a pre-determined section of the population, a cross-sectional research design is used. Furthermore, since the study will be conducted for only a single segment of the population i.e. Urban Population of Mumbai, we have used a **single cross sectional descriptive design**.

5.2 Sampling Design

5.2.1 Sample Population

Since the study is carried out to analyse the impulse buying behavior of shoppers specifically in the Fashion Industry, the population for our research constituted of the urban class population of Mumbai and New Delhi. Urban Area of a population can be categorized by urban morphology as cities, towns or suburbs and characterized by higher infrastructural development.

5.2.2 Sample Frame

Our sampling design did not as such require and use a sampling frame.

5.2.3 Sampling Method

Sampling Method essentially refers to the process of selecting a sample from the given population. This process can be divided into 2 types i.e. Probability and Non-Probability Method. Probability method is one wherein all the subjects of the population have an equal chance of getting selected as respondents. Whereas, non probability method is one wherein it is not known as to which individual will be selected as a representative from the population.

The sampling method used in this research is non-probability since all the respondents do not have an equal chance of being selected.

Non-probability method further consists of Convenience Sampling, Quota Sampling, Judgement Sampling and Snowball Sampling. As the name suggests, convenience sampling involves selecting the sample based on the respondents convenience. Quota Sampling involves fixation of specific quotas for the respondents, which need to be fulfilled. Judgement sampling is where the researcher uses her judgement and discretion to choose the respondents. Lastly, snowball sampling first collects data from the respondents at convenience and subsequently uses referrals to further collect the data.

Our research has used the Convenience Method of Non-probability Sampling since the samples have been selected based on our convenience.

5.3 Data Collection Method

5.3.1 Primary Data

The complete research is essentially based on primary data as the results are based on the data collected the given sample population as the research requires first hand data to answer the given questions.

5.3.2 Secondary Data

Secondary Data, in the form of various published articles, finding and case studies on the topic of Impulse shopping has also been used, specifically to validate and compare the findings derived out of primary data.

5.3.3 Type of Primary Research

Given that a descriptive research design is used, the data collection method is quantitative in nature as the findings of the research are required to be numerical in terms in order to facilitate an exact comparison and create concrete conclusions. Therefore, the has been conducted in the form of a structured survey in order to generate quantitative responses.

5.3.4 Type of Quantitative Method

An online survey, in the form of a custom webpage has been used to collect the data. The specific tool is "Google Forms" as in enables the user to create a custom structured questionnaire and easily share it online, across the targeted sample. The Questionnaire is attached in the appendices.

5.3.5 Time Period

The approximate time period for collecting the data was one week, after which the webpage was voluntarily closed from taking responses.

VI. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

6.1 Objective I

Various Internal and External Factors Affecting Fashion Related Impulse Shopping

6.2 Internal Factors

The following internal factors were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how the consumers felt while impulsive purchasing on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Least Important', 5 being 'Most Important' based on their past experience.

6.3 Moods

In order to broadly analyse the effect of different moods on a person's impulse apparel shopping behavior, we have considered two emotions for our analysis i.e. Happy and Sad.

a. Happy

Statement: "I tend to buy impulsively when I'm in a happy mood"

b. Sad

Statement: "I tend to shop impulsively when I'm in a sad mood"

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of Moods

MOODS	HAPPY	SAD
MEAN	2.94	1.95
STD DEV	1.628	1.695

Findings/Analysis: We can conclude that people tend to buy more when they are happy as compared to sad mood as happy as a mean of 2.94 versus the mean of sad which is 1.95, this data can be trusted because of minimal variation in the standard deviation of the 2 moods.

6.4 Gender

In order to analyse as to which gender is more likely to purchase impulsively, we studied the responses of both the gender separately to the question "On the basis of your past experiences of apparel shopping, how likely are you to buy something on an impulse? (One being least likely)"

Table 2: Descriptive analysis of Gender

GENDER	MEAN
MALE	3.02
FEMALE	2.89

In the paper by Mr Vishnu and Raheem they concluded that the male to female ratio for impulse shoppers are 3:1. In a paper by Mr Rasheed and his colleges they state that 61% of shoppers are Male while 39% are female. Both these instances support these findings that males tend to impulsively shop more than females.

Findings/Analysis: On the basis of gender we can conclude that males tend to shop more impulsively than females according to the past experiences of the consumers as 106 males have opted for values above mean and 91 females have opted for values above mean therefore males are more likely to impulsively shop than females. This is in agreement with the findings of the literature reviewed by us.

6.5 Influence of Friends and Family

Statement: "Friends and Family often influence my impulse buying behavior"

MEAN: 2.53

STD DEV:1.200

Findings/Analysis: Lastly, given the fact that the mean of this factor is 2.53, one can conclude that the respondents more or less disagreed with the fact that they are influenced by friends and family while experiencing

impulse buying behavior. This finding can be validated by a lower standard deviation depicting that most the respondents have similar responses.

6.6 External Factors

The following external factors were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how the consumers felt while impulsive purchasing on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Least Important', 5 being 'Most Important' based on their past experience.

1. Overall Shopping Environment

Mean-3.093

Standard Deviation-1.23

2. Promotional Schemes and Ongoing Discounts

Mean-3.3

Standard Deviation-1.9

3. Efforts of Sales Staff

Mean-2.7

Standard Deviation-1.13

4. Low Prices

Mean-3.35

Standard Deviation-1.32

Visual Merchandising

Mean-3.083

Standard Deviation-1.1

Table 3: Descriptive Analysis of External Factors

PARTICULARS	Overall Shopping Environment	Promotional Schemes and Ongoing Discounts	Efforts of sales staff	Low Prices	Visual Merchandising
MEAN	3.093	3.38	2.72	3.35	3.083
STANDARD DEVIATION	1.23	1.13	1.13	1.32	1.1

Findings/analysis: In external factors we can conclude that promotional schemes and discounts(mean:3.38) and low prices(mean:3.35) motivate customers to buy impulsively the most but due to lower standard deviation in promotional schemes(standard deviation:1.13) it seems to be the biggest motivator for the consumer to buy impulsively. we also notice that the consumers are least receptive or responsive towards efforts of sales staff(mean:2.72) and visual merchandising(mean:3.083).

In the paper by Anmol Rasheed and colleges they found that Schemes discounts and low prices were more attractive than all other factors they studied. In their findings promotional activities have the highest mean as compared to other factors namely store environment, payment facility, promotional activity and income level

6.7 Objective II

TO ANALYSE THE IMPULSE BUYING BEHAVIOR OF CONSUMERS TOWARDS DIFFERENT PRODUCT CATEGORIES

Table 4: Descriptive Analysis of Product Categories

CATEGORY	MEAN	STD DEV
COSMETICS	2.03	1.23
CLOTHING	3.51	1.24
FOOTWEAR	3.11	1.30
ACCESSORIES	2.99	1.33

Findings/Analysis: Here we can conclude that consumers are most likely to shop for clothing (mean of 3.51) on an impulse whereas cosmetics (mean of 2.03) seem to be the least likely to be purchased on an impulse. accessories have the highest standard dev, this indicates that the consumers are behaving in an extreme manner, that is they feel strongly and differently individually towards impulsive buying of accessories.

6.8 Objective III

The following product categories were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how the consumers felt while impulsive purchasing on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Least Important', 5 being 'Most Important based on their past experience.

1. Cosmetics

MEAN: 2.03

STD DEV: 1.23

2. Clothing

MEAN: 3.51

STD DEV: 1.24

3. Footwear

MEAN:3.11

STD DEV:1.30

4. Accessories

MEAN:2.99

STD DEV:1.33

To Analyse the post purchase feeling and behavior as a result impulse apparel buying behaviour.

Post Purchase Feelings

The following emotions were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how the consumers felt while impulsive purchasing.

Given below is the count of the options that the respondents opted for:

Table 5: Descriptive Analysis of Mode of Post Purchase Feeling

REGRET	22
HAPINESS	153
GUILT	27
EXCITEMENT	86
NOTHING / NOT SURE	8

Graph 1: Survey Response of Post Purchase Sentiments

(Source: Primary Data)

Findings/Analysis-From the data gathered we can deduce that a majority of the consumers were happy (153 of 300) after purchasing of clothing apparel impulsively which was followed by excitement (86 of 300). The least felt emotions were guilt (27 of 300) and regret (22 of 300). These facts indicate that most people are happy and excited after purchasing for clothing apparel impulsively whereas a small chunk of the sample were left regretting or guilty after the purchase.

Re Purchase Behavior

The following factors were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how likely the consumers would re purchase an apparel item which they previously impulsively purchased on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Least Important', 5 being 'Most Important based on their past experience, the graph depicting which is given below:

Graph 2: Survey Responses of Post Purchase Behavior

(Source: Primary Data)

MEAN: 3.037

STD DEV: 1.17

Findings/Analysis: Here we see that 11.2% of our sample was most likely going to re buy an apparel

item they have previously purchased impulsively; these are the most beneficial customers for a company. 12.2%

were least likely to do the same. companies need to target the 12.2% that is least likely and 18.7% that opted for 3/4 to increase re purchase income from customers.

6.9 Objective IV

To analyse the effects of growing E-commerce industry on impulse shopping behavior in the fashion industry, and the factors leading to this outcome.

6.9.1 Effect of Online Shopping on Impulse Buying Behavior

The growing role of e-commerce and how it affects consumer behaviour were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how the consumers felt while impulsive purchasing on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Least Important', 5 being 'Most Important' based on their past experience, the graph depicting which is given below:

Graph 3: Survey Responses of Impact of E-commerce on Impulse Buying Behavior

(Source: Primary Data)

MEAN- 3.4

STANDARD DEVIATION- 1.29

Findings/Analysis: we see the highest percentages 29% and 24.6% of consumers feel that online shopping has enhanced their impulsive shopping behaviour and we see a standard deviation of 1.29 which suggests that a majority of the sample thinks and responds to online shopping alike.

6.9.2 Factors Affecting Online Impulse Buying Behaviour

The following factors were considered while framing the questionnaire so as to measure how important the consumers felt these factors were to them and how they influenced them while impulsive purchasing on a scale of 1-5, 1 being 'Least Important', 5 being 'Most Important' based on their past experience.

In a paper by Umair Akram, Peng Hui, Muhammad Kaleem Khan, Chen Yan and Zubair Akram they found that likeness to online impulse shop was the

highest with a mean value of . 4.89 with a Standard deviation of 0.92.

1. Convenience
Mean-3.44
Standard Deviation-1.32
2. Variety
Mean-3.38
Standard Deviation-1.21
3. 24*7 Availability
Mean- 3.41
Standard Deviation-1.30
4. Heavy Advertising
Mean -2.72
Standard Deviation-1.41
5. Discounts and Promotional Schemes
Mean-3.62
Standard Deviation-1.21

Table 6: Descriptive Analysis of Factors Affecting Online Impulse Buying Behavior

PARTICULARS	Convenience	Variety	24*7 Availability	Heavy Advertising	Discounts and Promotional Schemes
MEAN	3.44	3.38	3.41	2.72	3.62

STANDARD DEVIATION	1.32	1.21	1.30	1.41	1.21
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Findings/Analysis: we see that promotional schemes(mean of 3.62) and convenience(mean of 3.44) have the highest mean and most impact on the consumers impulsive online shopping behavior. However promotional schemes have the lowest standard dev(1.21) that suggests that a majority of the consumers feel the same way and thus it is the most important factor affecting online impulsive shopping. On the other hand, consumers are least responsive to heavy advertising of products however it also has the highest standard deviation that suggests that consumers react differently and individually to heavy advertising.

VII. CONCLUSION

Targeting impulse buying has been a challenge for marketers, especially in the fashion domain, mainly due to its complex nature. The growing market and demand for fashion and apparel products can give companies a chance to capitalize on the impulse buying behavior of individuals. Our research, therefore, provides an insight and a quantitative study on the various aspects of Fashion related Impulsive Shopping focusing from its factors to its post purchase behavior as well. The empirical findings firstly showed that while males tend to indulge in more impulse shopping than females, both the genders tend to shop more impulsively when in a happy mood, as supported by existing literature. Moreover, promotional schemes and lower prices tend that have the maximum impact in triggering impulse buying behavior. Moreover, as opposed to the general belief that impulse buying leads to heavy post purchase dissonance, our research showed that maximum respondents were happy with their previous purchases and many would repurchase such impulsively bought apparel, Clothing and Footwear being the most impulsively purchased product category. Lastly, our research also briefly provided a descriptive insight on online impulse purchasing and the factors triggering it, with Convenience and Heavy Discounts being the most prominent triggers. In all, the research

attempted at studying the various dimensions related to fashion related impulse shopping and has further furnished certain specific recommendations, based on our findings.

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5. Visual Merchandising

1 2 3 4 5

Q8 Which of the following product categories are you more likely to shop impulsively

1. Cosmetics	1	2	3	4	5
2. Clothing	1	2	3	4	5
3. Footwear	1	2	3	4	5
4. Accessories	1	2	3	4	5

Q9 On the basis of your past apparel based impulse purchases, which of the following best describes your Post Purchase Feeling?

1. Regret
2. Happiness
3. Guilt
4. Excitement
5. Others:

Q10 Based on your past experiences, how likely are you to repurchase an apparel item (clothing, shoes, etc.) which you have previously purchased impulsively? (1 being 'Least Likely', 5 being 'Most Likely')

1 2 3 4 5

Q11 How often do you shop online for fashion products?

1. Once a month
2. Twice a month
3. Once a week
4. Twice a week
5. Others:

Q12 On a scale of 1 to 5, do you think the emergence of online shopping has enhanced your impulsive shopping behavior?

1 2 3 4 5

Q13 On a scale of 1-5, how much do these factors influence such online impulse buying behavior?

1. Convenience	1	2	3	4	5
2. Variety	1	2	3	4	5
3. 24*7 Availability	1	2	3	4	5
4. Heavy Advertising	1	2	3	4	5
5. Discounts and Promotional Schemes	1	2	3	4	5